

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	2011	B		Min: 62.363 Max: 63.589	1322 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1505-8	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION cut filled by 1306 + 1279	Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1306 + 1279
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1279	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: 1001 (bedrock)
Is filled by: 1306, 1279, 1283, 1385	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
 Conspicuous erosion along northern edges. Cut is cut into bedrock on the north; on the east it appears to cut through other features

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: Northern + Eastern Area B, on northern + eastern edges of house
 Shape: Linear, curves around structure

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations: In some places very irregular cut, with sloping sides (erosion?). Elsewhere very regular with square edges + very linear. See sections.

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:
 Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)
 Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:
 Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:
 Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)
 Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type
 Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)
 Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

INTERPRETATION

1320 Represents a construction or drainage trench for the northern wall of the structure in Area B. This wall has mostly been robbed out, but is still visible to the east + west. The level of the bedrock is higher to the north, so our cut appears also to have been related to the creation of a flat terrace for construction. Erosion has made the cut irregular in some places + entirely truncated elsewhere - only near the center of the trench are sharp edges well preserved. The trench continues beyond our excavation limit to the west, + curves around the structure to the east, where it is filled by 1279 (=1306).

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No
 Total volume of layer (buckets):
 Sample quantity (buckets):
 Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No
 If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):
 Size:

SIEVING: Yes No
 Total volume of layer (buckets):
 Sample quantity (buckets):
 Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY
 Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	J. FARR	on	28.6.2011
Revised by	CHM	on	28.6.2011
PDFd by		on	
Entered by		on	